

MULTICHANNEL COMPOSITION USING STATE-SPACE MODELS AND SONIFICATION

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ABSTRACT

This paper explores the use state-space models and real time sonification as a tool for electroacoustic composition. State-space models provide mathematical representations of physical systems, making possible to virtually capture a real life system behaviour in a matrix-vector equation.

The paper presents an inverted pendulum, a mass-spring-damper system, and a harmonic oscillator, implemented in Supercollider, and different real time multichannel sonification approaches, as well as ways of using them in electroacoustic composition.

1. INTRODUCTION

Sonification has become a very important tool to convey information and represent/analyse data using sound. In recent years a musical interest has developed as a result of the aesthetic awareness on the different ways of representing data in meaningful ways [1] [2] [3].

Mathematical models play a very important role in the sound synthesis field. For instance physical modelling, modal synthesis and digital waveguides aim to model the acoustic behaviour of sound producing objects [4] [5].

This paper shows the use of mathematical models of dynamic systems for the creation of synthetic sound, however this models don't represent the acoustic nature of such systems but rather motion behaviours to be sonified using abstract sound synthesis techniques.

This paper explores the uses of real time sonifications of state-space models as a source for electroacoustic composition. A motivation to use state-space models is finding ways to produce synthetic sound which evolves in an organic way.

Sonifying state-space models can be described as a parametric model based interactive sonification [6]. It is based on the implementation of physical systems, as mathematical models in their state-space form, and the possibility of exciting and sonifying them in real time. The advantage of the state-space form is that a vector containing the states of system can be available in real time, making simultaneously available several variables from the same system. The aim in these sonifications is not necessary accurately representing the system's behaviour, but rather looking for diverse

sound timbres, or behaviours when simultaneously mapping all system variables into sound generation, or sound transformation parameters. A multichannel approach is used to add an spatial element in the composition process.

2. STATE-SPACE REPRESENTATIONS

State-space mathematical models are a useful tool to represent dynamical physical system's behaviour in a compact way. Provided the system is linear and time invariant, it is possible to formulate a matrix equation that describes the systems behaviour. The matrix representation is called the state-space representation of a continuous system dynamics and can be written as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{x}(t) &= Ax(t) + Bu(t) \\ y(t) &= Cx(t) + Du(t)\end{aligned}\quad (1)$$

Where $x(t) \in R^n$ is the n-dimensional state vector, $u(t) \in R^m$ is the m-dimensional input vector, and $y(t) \in R^p$ is the p-dimensional output vector. A and B are constant matrixes, containing information about the characteristics defining the system. C determines which states are the model outputs, and D is a feedback matrix connecting directly the output to the input [7].

The state-space models used for this paper consist of one input and n outputs, depending of the nature of the system. The implemented models are sampled digital representations of the continuous systems.

The sampled version of (1) with sampling period T_s can be represented as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}x(k+1) &= \Phi x(k) + \Gamma u(k) \\ y(k) &= Cx(k) + Du(k)\end{aligned}\quad (2)$$

Where $\Phi = e^{aT_s}$ and $\Gamma = \int_0^{T_s} e^{As} ds$ are obtained by considering a zero order sample and hold circuit, and the simplified notation k refers to a general time $t_k \in \{t_0, t_1 \dots t_N\}$ [8].

3. SYSTEM DESCRIPTION AND IMPLEMENTATION

The three specific systems are described briefly to understand the physical nature of their behaviour. Although the descriptions show the continuous systems, the implemented ones are digital representations in the state-space form (2).

Matrixes A and B were calculated using MatLab. The specific variable values will be shown for each system¹. The corresponding matrixes Φ and Γ for a specific sampling period were calculated using MatLab.

3.1 Mass-Spring-Damper

The mass-spring-damper system is depicted in Fig. 1. The input to the system is the force $f(t)$ applied to the mass. The system outputs $y(t)$ are the mass position (displacement) and velocity [9].

Figure 1. Implemented Mass Spring Damper system illustration.

When a force is applied to the mass, it will start a unidimensional movement in the direction of the applied force. This movement has an oscillatory elastic nature due to the action of the spring (k), and will be dampen due to the action of the damper (c). The movement will eventually stop if no further force is applied.

The implemented sampled version of this system with $m = 1kg$, $k = 1N/m$, $c = 0.2Ns/m$, sampling period $T_s = 0.1$ secs, and in the form (2) has the following system matrixes:

$$\Phi = \begin{bmatrix} 0.99503 & 0.09884 \\ -0.09884 & 0.97526 \end{bmatrix}, \Gamma = \begin{bmatrix} 0.00496 \\ 0.09884 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (3)$$

$$C = [1, 1], \quad D = 0$$

3.2 Inverted Pendulum

The inverted pendulum system is depicted in Fig 2. The system consists of an inverted pendulum mounted on a mobile cart. If the system is not controlled, the pendulum will fall over when an input force is applied to the cart. For this reason a controlled system was implemented [10]. The aim of the controller is that when the cart is displaced to a desired position, the pendulum is able to come back to equilibrium vertical position. The input of the system is a number representing a desired position for the cart (meters). The outputs are the cart's displacement (meters), cart's velocity, the pendulum angle (radians) and pendulum angular velocity.

The inverted pendulum with $M = 0.5$, $m = 0.2$, $I = 0.006$, $l = 0.3$ and a sampling period $T_s = 0.02$ secs is

Figure 2. Implemented Inverted Pendulum physical representation.

represented by the following matrixes:

$$\Phi = \begin{bmatrix} 1.0056 & 0.0130 & -0.0085 & -0.0017 \\ 1.1263 & 1.6069 & -1.7003 & -0.3420 \\ 0.0141 & 0.0076 & 0.9800 & 0.0057 \\ 2.8168 & 1.5178 & -4.0073 & 0.1460 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (4)$$

$$\Gamma = \begin{bmatrix} -0.0056 \\ -1.1263 \\ -0.0141 \\ -2.8168 \end{bmatrix}, C = [1, 1, 1, 1], \quad D = 0$$

3.3 Harmonic Oscillator

A harmonic oscillator system representation is depicted in Figure 3. It consists of a mass attached to a spring and connected to a rigid wall in a non friction environment. If no force is applied, the mass remains in its equilibrium state. If a force is applied to the mass, an elastic force due to the spring will try to restore the equilibrium state, producing a periodic movement. The system input is therefore a force applied to the mass, and the outputs are the mass unidimensional position, and velocity [11].

Figure 3. Harmonic Oscillator physical representation.

The digital implemented system with $\sqrt{k/m} = 133$,² and $T_s = \pi/32$, is represented by the following matrixes:

$$\Phi = \begin{bmatrix} 0.8819 & 0.4714 \\ -0.4714 & 0.8819 \end{bmatrix}, \Gamma = \begin{bmatrix} 0.1181 \\ 0.4714 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (5)$$

$$C = [1, 1], \quad D = 0$$

¹ For more details on the calculation of matrixes A, B, C, D consult the specific references for each system.

² This ratio guarantees a solution for the motion equations [12].

3.4 SuperCollider Implementation

The implementation in SuperCollider was achieved by creating a class to handle linear algebra matrix operations. The class arguments are the matrixes Φ, Γ, C, D ; and the numeric input u . The class outputs are systems state vector x . State variables update in real time according to the sampling time parameter T_s , which can also be modified in real time.

The implemented systems work according to the following criteria: (1) All systems require only one numeric input; (2) the systems state-space is the set of variables in the vector $x(k)$ describing the systems behaviour (i.e. position and velocity in the mass-spring damper system); (3) the output vector depends on the matrix C, the elements in this vector represent physical variables of the system; (4) the systems current output depends on the current input value, a previous input value, the current state and a previous state; (5) the system's output vector updates according to a sample period time parameter; (6) the numeric input u , and sample period T_s can be changed in real time: the output state vector updates accordingly to this values.

The implementations were tested using SuperCollider version 3.6.5, on a 2.3 GHz Intel Core I7 processor, OS X version 10.8.5. The average time to compute a state vector for the inverted pendulum is 99.681998108281e-06 secs, and for the mass-spring-damper system and harmonic oscillator 71.91300028353e-06 secs.

4. SONIFICATION AND STATE-SPACE MODELS

4.1 Sound Synthesis

A first sonification approach is generating sound synthesis. This can done by simultaneously mapping all outputs from a chosen system into different parameters of the same synthesiser. Even though AM and FM techniques are used to create this sonifications, sound becomes part of the model dynamics and evolves in an organic way as the modulating signals come from the same system.

As an example, a combination of AM/FM synthesiser was used to sonify the mass-spring-damper system. As the model behaviour is available in real time, it is possible, to "virtually play it" by applying numerical inputs in real time.

Having in mind that the output variables represent position and velocity, it is possible to design a synthesiser to sonify them. Fig. 4 shows the stereo sonification schematic diagram. The position is mapped into the $f1$ parameter, it is scaled and used to modulate in frequency a sine wave. The velocity is also mapped into a $f2$ parameter, after scaling, it modulates in frequency a saw tooth wave. The scaling values for both variables are shown in Table 1.

Additional scaling factors are added in the synthesiser, this

Variable	original range (abs)	scaled range
position	0-16000	30-16000
velocity	0-6000	200-6200

Table 1. Scaling values for the the mass-spring-damper system variables.

is represented by the different coefficients in the schematic diagram. This gives diversity to the sound although both channels are related as both are sonifications of the same model. Once the synthesiser is set-up, the numerical input

Figure 4. Mass-Spring-Damper system stereo sonification example.

can be changed in real time and the sound will evolve in time according to the system's nature. What is expected is a sinusoidal behaviour exponentially decaying. This means that if the input doesn't change, the output states will reach a stationary state with almost no oscillations. A recording of this sonification process can be found at ³.

Using the same synthesiser and same scaling values it is also possible to sonify the harmonic oscillator. This system is also oscillatory, but as it doesn't have any damping element, it will continue oscillating without decaying with an amplitude proportional to the input force applied. Even though the same synthesiser is used, the sound has a different behaviour, making it possible to have variations of the same timbre. This fact can be heard at ⁴.

4.2 Multichannel approach

It is also possible to expand the stereo sonification idea to a multichannel approach. This can be achieved by creating multichannel synthesisers all driven simultaneously by the same model. As an example, a 4-channel sonification for the inverted pendulum is depicted in Fig. 5. The 4-ch synthesiser is designed to have three control variables. Pendulum position, cart velocity and pendulum angle are scaled and mapped to simultaneously control these variables. Table 2 shows the scaled values for the inverted pendulum.

The cart position is mapped so it modulates in frequency a sine wave, the velocity and angle modulate a low frequency triangle wave. Extra scaling factors are added per channel in the synthesiser, as shown in Fig. 5. The extra scaling factors have the purpose of creating sound families by placing related sounds in different channels (speakers), to involve the spatial factor.

³ <https://dl.dropboxusercontent.com/u/88409515/sonif1.aif>

⁴ <https://dl.dropboxusercontent.com/u/88409515/sonif2.aif>

Variable	original range (abs)	scaled range
position	0-16000	80-6480
velocity	0-5700	8-1148
angle	0-13000	2.5-132.5

Table 2. Scaling values for the inverted pendulum.

The expected behaviour is an oscillating movement that will settle when it reaches the desired position according to the real time input. Velocity will settle at 0 when the final position is reached, and the same will happen for the angle, as the pendulum has to end up in a vertical position. This means that after a change in the input, sound will vary according to changes in position, velocity and angle; if the input doesn't change, the sound will reach a stationary state. A recording of this sonification example can be found at ⁵.

Figure 5. Inverted Pendulum system. 4-ch sonification example.

4.3 Sound transformation

Sonification can also be achieved by transforming sound. As an example, a VOSIM oscillator is used to sonify the spring-mass-damper system ⁶. The position is scaled and mapped into the pulse trigger frequency whereas the velocity is mapped into the VOSIM frequency. Velocity is also used to modify a time delay parameter that affects the VOSIM oscillator. Fig. 6 shows a schematic diagram for this example. A fragment of this sonification can be found at ⁷.

5. COMPOSING WITH STATE-SPACE MODELS

5.1 Sonifications and Sound Synthesis

As the model's behaviour is available in real time, a combination synthesiser-sonification can be seen as an instrument

⁵ <https://dl.dropboxusercontent.com/u/88409515/sonif3.aif>

⁶ VOice SIMulation, "... is a signal consisting of sequences of \sin^2 pulses each of the same duration and decreasing amplitude" [13].

⁷ <https://dl.dropboxusercontent.com/u/88409515/sonif4.aif>

Figure 6. Mass-spring-damper system. Sound synthesis and sound transformation 8-ch sonification example.

that can be played in real time. Depending on the mapping and synthesiser complexity, it is possible to generate different gestures, textures [14] and timbres.

This implies that the composition process includes a sound synthesis design step which involves choosing a model to sonify; awareness of the model's behaviour to achieve meaningful mappings of the different parameters (knowing numeric range of the outputs for different inputs and consider this when scaling variables); and experimenting with pairs model - synthesiser to explore behaviour and timbre possibilities for different inputs.

So far only the input-output aspect of the models has been discussed. However, there is a third factor included in the implementation and that is the sample period T_s . This parameter controls how often the output states update according to the input. Even though this parameter could remain fixed, it is possible to change it in real time to virtually "time stretch" or expand the system's behaviour, or even more, to freeze the system time evolution, making it possible to time stretch, expand, or freeze timbres.

Fig. 7 shows an interface created in Supercollider to interact with sonification synthesisers and model parameters in real time. The state-space input window allows the user to interact with the models by changing the input parameters according to Table 3.

Symbol	Parameter
t1	Sampling period value in secs (0.01-1)
uc	Model input value 0 -10
uc1	Model input value 0 -1000
uc2	Model input value 0 -15000

Table 3. Interface parameter to interact in real time with state-space models.

The total input to the model is $U = uc + uc1 + uc2$; this combination is useful to have different input resolutions.

Figure 7. Supercollider interface for real time interaction with state-space models and sonification synthesizers.

The buttons labeled as “preset 0” to “preset 6” trigger the models real time evolution, for different sonification presets⁸. If a button is active, the chosen model updates in real time; if not active, the model remains in the latest updated state. The interface also allows switching between the models in the menu. This is be useful when sonifying different models using the same synthesiser.

If the preset buttons are inactive, the selected model is frozen, meaning the current state is frozen, therefore timbre is frozen. In this condition it is also possible to manually change the synthesiser parameters. For example in Fig. 7, “freq”, “rate”, etc. That means manually manipulating the timbre once the model has brought the synthesiser to a particular timbre.

5.2 Sonic Outcomes

Even though stereo sonifications can create interesting timbres, the multichannel sonification approach allows experimenting with timbre and space in a wider sense.

One possibility is the creation of sound families by placing numerically related sounds, a different one per speaker, but all controlled by the same model. An example of this is the sonification depicted in Fig. 5. In this case timbre also includes the spatial factor.

A second option is generating multichannel gesture and texture. This can be controlled by manipulating the sampling period parameter T_s in the model input: if short, the models arrive faster to a stationary state, creating gesture;

if T_s is larger, sound evolves slowly creating smooth transitions and texture.

In addition, it is possible to map state-space variables into panning parameters to create gestural spatial effects.

5.3 Composition Possibilities

Once a satisfactory sonification is achieved, real time interactions can be recorded and used in fixed media or mixed media compositions. Some possibilites are including directly recorded sonification excerpts, they may be as long as desired; splitting multichannel sonification recordings; spatially rearranging them or using only selected audio channels; and applying further sound transformations to any of the above.

5.4 Example: Time Paradox

5.4.1 Sonifications and Structure

Time Paradox (2015) is an 8-channel fixed media piece composed using sonifications of the mass-spring damper system and singing bowls stereo recordings. The sonifications where designed to fit in stems of 4 or 8 channels. This offers the possibilites of locating sound families in different spatial locations when using 4-channel sonifications, and to create more atmospheric textures of related sounds when using 8-channel approaches.

The sonifications are based on a 4-channel pulse wave synthesiser (details not shown in this paper), 8-channel FM granular synthesiser, the synthesiser depicted in Fig. 6, and the 8-channel VOSIM synthesiser depicted in Fig. 8.

For the VOSIM sonification the system variables were pre-scaled with the values shown in Table 1. The mass position controls the trigger frequency for each pulse, the velocity controls the wave frequency and also controls the number of squared sine-waves to use in each pulse⁹.

Figure 8. Mass-spring-damper VOSIM sonification for Time Paradox.

⁸ It is possible to add as many presets as desired.

⁹ <http://doc.scode.org/Classes/VOSIM.html>

The GrainFM synthesiser consists on granular synthesis with frequency modulated sine tones¹⁰. The system states control the synthesiser parameters as follows: position mapped into grain trigger rate and carrier frequency; velocity mapped into modulating frequency.

The synthetic sound materials were created using the interface shown in Fig. 7.

Regarding sound materials, the piece consists of two sections. Fig. 9 shows the sound material structure per section. Section 1 includes direct recordings of sonification fragments, such as FM, Pulse, VOSIM + delay and fragments of singing bowls. Section 2 consists on split versions of the FM synthesizer, this means using different pairs of selected channels and relocating them spatially; unmodified recording of 8ch VOSIM fragments, and stereo and 4-channel expansion of singing bowls.

However, it was necessary to create transitions between sections and musical ideas. A shaped 8ch noise synthesiser was used as transition material and it is not a sonification of the system. A stereo version of Time Paradox can be found at¹¹.

Figure 9. Time Paradox sound material structure.

6. CONCLUSION

The paper illustrates the use of state-space models in composition. Sonified state-space models offer new possibilities for creating multichannel sound materials for electroacoustic composition. As the physical systems behaviour is available in real time, a sonified state-space model can be seen as virtual instrument that can be played and recorded in real time.

They also present the possibility of creating evolving timbres as sound "obeys" the systems behaviour. This is particularly interesting when mapping simultaneously all variables of a system into sound parameters. The spatial element is also important, as multichannel sonifications can be designed fitting stems of mono, stereo or any number up to 8 channels.

One of the main advantages of using sonified models, is that sound evolves in a more organic way, as the models obey laws of physics, preventing them for abrupt changes. However, it is also possible to slow down, speed up or freeze the time evolution, or to "virtually" apply input forces that would not be possible in real life, providing different

possibilities in timbre and sound evolution, such as gesture, texture, or smooth variations.

Regarding the composition process, untransformed recordings can be included as part of fixed media or mixed media pieces, but also further sound transformations can be applied as well as multichannel split or spatial rearrangements.

As a state-space framework has been developed in Supercollider, additional physical systems can be easily implemented, offering new sonification-composition possibilities for electroacoustic composition.

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¹⁰ <http://doc.sccode.org/Classes/GrainFM.html>

¹¹ <https://soundcloud.com/rosalia-soria/time-paradox-stereo>

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